

Determinants of Trade Flow in the Democratic Republic of the Congo

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Abstract

In general, the mathematical function used is the logarithm function to study the Determinants of foreign trade. The model is based on an "imports" function and an "exports" function. It breaks down exports according to world demand and external competitiveness and imports according to gross domestic product and domestic competitiveness. It is a reduced model which makes it possible to study both imports and exports. In our case we have limited ourselves to studying the function of imports. The dependence of the economy on imports of products requires in the Democratic Republic of the Congo which deteriorates the trade balance. To this end, stabilized the exchange rate should not be short-lived. The revival of the economy through sufficient national production in auspicious business would contain external and unexpected shocks to the economy.

Keywords: imports, foreign trade, exchange rate, trade balance

1. Introduction

Monetary policy is the action by which the monetary authority, generally the central bank, acts on the supply of money in order to fulfill its objective of price stability. It also strives to achieve the other objectives of monetary policy, described as the Keynesian triangle: growth, full employment, external balance [Marcel, 2016]. Monetary policy differs from fiscal policy. Monetary policy may aim to maintain the exchange rate of the national currency with one currency. Fixed exchange rates can be obtained by the central bank by selling and buying foreign currency overnight to reach the target rate.

[Marcel, 2016].

An effective balance of payment management requires a better understanding of the behavior of goods and services flow. There are quite a few evidence that the trade flow is influenced by the relative price (domestic and import price) and the exchange rate.

Hence is crucial for the policy maker to get knowledge of how each of these determinants affects the trade flow (magnitude and direction).As well, it is worth uncovering which one of these determinants (relative price or exchange rate) can be more effective as a policy tool, to improve the balance of payment.

Hence the objective of this study is to: Estimate the aggregate import demand function in DRC;

To determine the impacts of a price change and exchange rate influence on the import demand function;

And to investigate which one of these determinants affect the most the import demand function.

The increase in imports leads to a deterioration in the trade balance to signify a decrease in net exports. This graph shows us the evolution of trade or that of the trade balance.

Graphic: Evolution balance of payments (billion \$ US)

Source: IMF

This graph traces four phases in the evolution of the level of the trade balance.

During the first phase from 1979 to 1984, the trade balance began to improve and reached equilibrium, a zero balance around 1984. The level of trade went up to 20% in 1980 following an adopted policy to avoid a shift in demand for substitute products, the index of minerals exported from the Congo has thus risen [Central Bank of Congo, 1984].

The second phase, starting from 1985 to 2001, was characterized by a deterioration in the trade balance, namely a decrease in exports. [Central Bank of Congo, 2001].

The third phase, from 2002 to 2018, is the one that appears to be the longest. It is characterized by the deterioration of the trade balance as time goes by. The foreign trade of the Democratic Republic of the Congo (with the rest of the world) has recorded for several years the deterioration of the trade balance. This deterioration in overall transactions is due to the deceleration of both import spending and the dependence of the economy on imports of basic necessities; the drop in export earnings due to the fall in international commodity prices; the undiversified structure of the national economy; the implementation of ineffective public policies; the business climate that is not conducive to investment and the political environment that is not very reassuring [FEC, 2017]. In fact, this deterioration in the export price index relative to imports continues in 2017 as well as in 2018 [Central Bank of Congo, 2018].

2. Literature Review

Generally there are two main types of foreign trade strategies. It is about promoting exports and import substitution to which we can add the strategy of food self-sufficiency. The export promotion aims to increase export earnings by stimulating measures which have the effect of encouraging exports and consequently of widening the base of exportable products [Gillis, Perkins, Roemer, Donald, 1990]. These stimulus measures mentioned above should be based more on price influences (for example, the application of a realistic exchange rate) than on quantitative controls (such as subsidies to production or to exporters). Nevertheless we can consider in our opinion that the application of a realistic exchange rate allows the exporters to sell more and to take advantage of the prices offered on the international market [Spire, 2012].

The proponents of export promotion "maintain that tariffs do not stimulate production for the international market on the one hand and on the other hand that subsidies can weigh heavily on state budgets and are generally difficult to make to admit on the political level" [Yeats, 1996]. It is important to note, however, that while price-based incentives stimulate production for export, they must at the same time allow exporting industries to purchase the intermediate goods and raw materials they need [Kodila, 2008]. In the situation where the foreign supply costs expressed in national currency are too high, exports will be less competitive on the international market. In addition, a genuine export promotion policy must be accompanied by a relatively open and liberalized trade regime, since price liberalization lowers barriers preventing exports, etc. In other words, this foreign trade regime must be capable of encouraging all producers to enter the export market [Weidenfeld, Spire, 2015]. While the export promotion strategy recommends trade liberalization and price-based incentives to increase exports, the "import substitution" scheme, on the other hand, aims to encourage local production of a commodity competing with import by subsidizing it.

This encouragement to domestic production is reflected in quantitative controls and regulations governing imports such as the imposition of customs tariffs, direct import restrictions, overvalued exchange rates and other measures to discourage imports [Enyimo, 2008]. There are many criticisms made of export promotion advocates of the import substitution

strategy. Indeed, it is argued that if the import substitution strategy can limit dependence on imports of final consumer goods, it does, however, lead to dependence on imports of capital goods, intermediate goods and raw materials intended for production in developing or underdeveloped countries [Yawidi, 2008]. These so-called imports cannot be reduced without compromising national economic growth. Thus, although liberating the country's economy, the import substitution strategy often leads to an even more dependent national economy than in the case of the export promotion strategy.

Furthermore, it is pointed out that in most developing or underdeveloped countries, industrialization which is sheltered from protectionism, leads to the creation of businesses at high cost prices [Lopez, 2012].

3. Model Specification and data source

The simple way to formulate the import demand function is to relate it to the country's gross domestic products (GDP), the relative price as well as the exchange rate.

But given that the homogeneity assumption or perfect substitutability appears to be strong, it is wise to make the difference between the effect of a domestic price change on imports and the effect of import price on imports.

Hence our import demand function can be specified as follow:

$$\ln M_t = \alpha + \beta \ln Y_t + \gamma_1 \ln DP_t + \gamma_2 \ln MP_t + \lambda E_t + \varepsilon_t$$

Where

M_t stands for annual import quantity

Y_t : gross domestic products

DP : Domestic price

MP : import price

E_t : exchange rate

ε_t : error term (others factors explaining import demand function but not taken into consideration in our model).

Since our function is specified in logarithm, the issue related to stationarity of the series is not more that relevant, hence the data become appropriate for the OLS estimation method. Furthermore, the parameters β , γ_1 and γ_2 are viewed as income and price elasticities.

It is expected that **β will be positive**, as the country aggregate import increases with the gross domestic product (GDP) As well, as well γ_1 is expected to be positive as the country import increases with the domestic price.

But we expect γ_2 to be negative as the country aggregate imports decrease with the import price

It is also worth to underline that **λ is expected** to be positive, in fact, in our model E stands for a nominal exchange rate; defined as units of foreign currency per unit of the domestic currency, hence an increase in E implies an appreciation of the domestic currency and therefore a rise in import flow.

We make things simple by not accounting for the lag existing between the change in price or in the exchange rate and the change in import demand function and income.

4. Results Analysis.

As part of this analysis, we use annual data, ranging from 1978 to 2018, containing 41 observations for each variable, collected from different monthly reports from the Central Bank of Congo.

Table:

Dependent Variable: LNIMP
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 03/27/20 Time: 19:01
 Sample: 1978 2018
 Included observations: 38

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-10.45186	2.004923	-5.213099	0.0000
LNGDP	0.913831	0.159853	5.716678	0.0000
LNDP	0.255604	0.287130	0.890201	0.3798
LNMP	-0.150477	0.204095	-0.737293	0.4662
LNEXCH	1.420779	0.292412	4.858832	0.0000
R-squared	0.805841	Mean dependent var		3.063725
Adjusted R-squared	0.782306	S.D. dependent var		0.935826
S.E. of regression	0.436635	Akaike info criterion		1.302639
Sum squared resid	6.291440	Schwarz criterion		1.518111
Log likelihood	-19.75014	Hannan-Quinn criter.		1.379302
F-statistic	34.24088	Durbin-Watson stat		0.745036
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

As already stated, the use of logarithm function smooth's data series and makes it appropriate for the estimation using to Ordinarily Least Squared method.

The estimation results are broadly in accordance with our expectations;

In fact, the OLS estimation results show that 1% change in the country gross domestic products (GDP) induces more than 91% change in imports, 1% rise in domestic price leads to 25% increase in the country import; 1% increase in import price leads to 15% fall in imports while 1% increase in exchange rate induces more than 100% change in imports of DRC, the import flows in DRC are very sensible to the exchange rate.

Though the p-values of the domestic and import price coefficients are not statistically significant, the overall model fits the data generating process well, as shown by the R-square and the adjusted R-square that are 0.80 and 0.78 respectively.

The assumption about non-homogeneity or the difference between the impact of the domestic price and the import price change on the import flows also holds; though the coefficients are not statically significant.

Besides, the estimation outcomes indicate that the impact of the exchange rate on the import flows in far important than the impact of the prices change; hence the exchange rate can be an effective tool to influence the flow of imports promptly In overall, the model appears to be reliable for forecasting, the residuals analysis from the OLS estimation are not correlated, where the residuals diagnostics show the p-values set all above 0.05

Conclusion

During this work, the aim was to estimate the effects of price changes and the influence of the exchange rate on the import demand function. The estimation results are significant with the exception of two variables which are: the coefficients of domestic prices and import prices are not significant. We have found that the impact of the high-interest exchange rate on price changes is how we conclude that the exchange rate can be an effective instrument for stimulating the flow of imports. The stabilization of the exchange rate should not be short-lived. To do this, economic decision-makers should, in addition to the speech of an advertising nature, focus on transforming the economic structure of the country with primacy over investments in agriculture and industries with strong value chains.

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